

Gall midge damage at rice panicle stage

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Gall midge damage to rice panicles and spikelets was first recorded at Raipur, Madhya Pradesh, during 1974 and 1978 kharif. In 1982 kharif, panicles and spikelets of 153 late transplanted tall and semi-dwarf popular varieties were seriously damaged by gall midge. We began varietal screening to isolate a source of gall midge resistance and to identify damage symptoms.

Two rows of 18 hills of each variety screened were transplanted 23 Aug 1982. Hills with panicle infestation, infested panicles, infested spikelets, and healthy panicles were recorded (Table 1). About 37% of hills, 21% of panicles, and 0.4% of spikelets were infested.

Of varieties screened for resistance, only Madhuri, Phalgun, and Surekha did not have gall midge-infested panicles or spikelets in all three plantings (Table 2). However, Madhuri was highly susceptible to gall midge at tillering stage. All hills of local tall varieties Safri 17, Basmati

Table 1. Gall midge damage to panicles and spikelets in staggered plantings, 1982 kharif, Raipur, India.

Sowing date	Varieties planted (no.)	Hills (no.)	Panicles (no.)	Infestation (%)		
				Hill	Panicle	Spikelet
22 Jun	146	2,971	14,845	34	16	0.6
12 Jul	153	5,436	29,686	37	17	0.3
5 Aug	81	1,862	7,690	41	29	0.3
Mean				37	21	0.4

370, Khao Dawk Mali, and Rati were infested.

Panicles and spikelets of varieties resistant to gall midge at vegetative stage showed varying degrees of susceptibility (Table 2).

We described the damage symptoms. The flag-leaf sheath is distorted, twisted, and crinkled with blunt or curved tips, atrophied or without leaf blade, and tissue paper thin. The penultimate leaf suppresses the flag leaf sheath and falsely represents the flag leaf. It tightly entangles the flag leaf, inhibits panicle exertion, and prevents spikelet fertilization to varying degrees. Levels of sterility in susceptible Bd 200 varied from 53% to 62%. □

Table 2. Gall midge damage to panicles and spikelets of midge-resistant varieties.

Variety	Infestation (%)		
	Hill	Panicle	Spikelet
R2384 (R68-1/Jaya)	1.0	1.0	0.0
R35-2752 (IR22/W1263)	7.0	1.0	0.0
R35-2750 (IR22/W1263)	6.0	1.0	0.0
Siam 29	21.0	12.0	1.0
Bangoli-5 (RPW6-17)	19.0	9.0	1.0
Mean	11.0	5.0	0.3

Pest management and control WEEDS

Tolerance of rice weeds for natural flood-water submergence

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We studied the effect of natural flood-water on growth of dryland and wetland rice weeds.

During early Sep 1982, much of the AAI farm was flooded by river water. After floodwater receded, weed growth on dryland and wetland rice fields was observed. Ten random samples of each weed species on the farm were observed and growth stage, plant height, and nature of submergence were recorded.

In dryland rice fields, which had 60 cm floodwater for 3 days, 13 weed

Table 1. Effect of submergence in 60cm floodwater depth for 3 days on dryland rice weeds.

Weed species	Growth stage	Plant height (cm)	Nature of submergence	Remarks
Broadleaf weeds				
<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) R. Br. ex. Roth	Flowering	21	Submerged	Unaffected
<i>Biophytum sensitivum</i> (L.) Dc.	Vegetative	5	- do -	- do -
<i>B. sensitivum</i> (L.) Dc.	Flowering	8	- do -	- do -
<i>Cleome viscosa</i> L.	Fruiting	95	Partially submerged	Complete defoliation and death of the plant
Convolvulus arvensis L.				
<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L.	Vegetative	16	Submerged	Unaffected
<i>Lindernia Ciliata</i> (Colsm.) Penn.	Flowering	26	- do -	- do -
<i>Lindernia crustacea</i> (L.) F. Muell.	Vegetative	6	- do -	- do -
<i>Oldenlandia corymbosa</i> L.	Vegetative	6	- do -	- do -
<i>Phyllanthus niruri</i> L.	Vegetative	12	- do -	- do -
<i>Phyllanthus urinaria</i> L.	Fruiting	51	- do -	- do -
	Fruiting	75	Partially submerged	- do -

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